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Research Article

RISK FACTOR ASSESSMENT FOR PRE-ECLAMPSIA: A CASE CONTROL STUDY

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Abstract:

Foundation: Knowledge and ID of hazard factors for preeclampsia will help in estimat-ing every lady's individualized hazard and perhaps decrease the repeat danger of preeclamp-sia. So this examination was led to evaluate and look at the socio-statistic profile of ladies with and without preeclampsia and to decide the hazard factors related with pre-eclampsia. Strategy: This Hospital based Case control logical examination was led among 180 preeclampsia case and 180 control subjects at Bahawal Victoria Hospital , from June 2017to May 2018. Results: Bivariate examination found that preeclampsia was fundamentally connected with country living arrangement ($p=0.033$), joint family type ($p=0.025$), low training of head of family($p=0.007$), youthful age at menarche (11-12years) ($p<0.001$) Anemia ($P=0.034$) and pri-miparity ($p<0.001$), Family history of preeclampsia ($p<0.001$) and hypertension ($p=0.007$) and Non veg. diet ($p=0.042$). Preeclampsia was not observed to be essentially connected with histo-ry of past premature birth, entomb pregnancy period and sex of last offspring of multiparous ladies and ANC attributes, TT vaccination, IFA tablets, twin pregnancy or gestational diabetes. In the various relapse investigation, Age >30 years, Preobese (BMI=25-29.9), fat (BMI $\geq$ 30 Kg/m²), Primiparity, time of menarche at 12 years and country home were observed to be indepen-imprint chance variables related with Preeclampsia. End: Age>30 years, Preobese, Obese, Primiparity, early time of menarche (12 years) and Rural home were found as noteworthy pre-dictor for advancement of Preeclampsia. A large portion of these components are non modifiable, however can be utilized to screen ladies amid antenatal visits to distinguish those at higher danger of Preeclampsia

Key words: Preeclampsia, Risk Factor, Pregnancy.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hypertensive issue of pregnancy are a standout amongst the most well-known reasons for maternal and fetal grimity and mortality representing in excess of 40,000 maternal passings overall annually.¹ In creating nations, it causes around 33% of maternal mor-tality.² Pakistan represented 19% of maternal passings worldwide.

Preeclampsia (PE) has remained a noteworthy general wellbeing risk in both created and creating coun-tries,⁵ be that as it may, the effect of the infection is felt all the more seriously in creating nations, where treatment might be incapable because recently introduction of cases. Despite the fact that pre-eclampsia is certainly not an absolutely preventable condition, its initial recognition and appropriate treatment can avoid severity,⁶ Unclear etiology and the unpre-dictable nature of the infection further compound the situ-ation.⁵ The frequency of PE ranges from 2% to 10%.⁴⁻⁷ WHO gauges the occurrence of preeclampsia to be multiple times higher in creating nations (2.8% of live births) than in created nations (0.4%).⁸ Pre-eclampsia has been related with expanded danger of unfriendly fetal, neonatal and maternal results in-cluding Antepartum and Postpartum drain, Acute renal and Hepatic disappointment, eclamptic seizures, stroke, Placental unexpectedness, HELLP disorder Heart

disappointment, DIC, Multiple organ disappointments and Maternal death.⁹⁻¹² Fetal inconveniences incorporate Fetal trouble, Intrauterine development hindrance, Preterm birth, Still-birth, Perinatal passing and Neonatal asphyxia.¹¹⁻¹⁵ The components that have been proposed to impact the danger of pre-eclampsia in different investigations incorporate Diabetes and Gestational Diabetes,¹²⁻¹⁴⁻¹⁶⁻¹⁸ Obesity,¹⁹ Multiple pregnancy.^{17,18} Personal and family ancestry of pre-ec-lampsia,²⁰ unending infections,²¹ UTI,² First pregnancy and Older maternal age or Younger than 20 years age,² Renal illness and immune system disorder,^{16,17} delayed interim between pregnancies²⁻¹⁸ and His-tory of fetus removal ⁸ and maternal diet.²²

Basis: Knowledge and ID of socio-statistic and clinical hazard factors for PE will help in evaluating every lady's individualized hazard and enable antenatal observation to be aimed at these ladies and guide the human services suppliers for coun-seling of such ladies and perhaps lessen the repeat rences danger of PE if some modifiable hazard factors (like stoutness) are available.

While most investigations have been attempted in high-in-come settings, a few irregularities exist, particularly in creating settings where pre-eclampsia chance fac-tors have been investigated less. Moreover, conditions, for example, extreme frailty and absence of antenatal consideration that are increasingly pervasive in less created locales require further investiga-tion and approval of discoveries.

Points and destinations were to evaluate and look at the socio-statistic profile of ladies with and without preeclampsia and to decide the hazard factors related with preeclampsia

METHODOLOGY:

This Hospital based Case control expository examination was directed at Bahawl victoria hospital bwp ,from June 2017 to May 2018. 180 preeclampsia case and 180 control subjects were incorporated into the examination. Test measure was determined at alpha mistake 0.05 and control 80%, taking the normal Odds proportion for family ancestry of Hypertension as a hazard factor of preeclampsia as 5.48 and extent of control subjects with Family History of Hyper-strain as 0.02.²³

Case gathering: Woman confessed to post natal ward who conveyed amid going before 2 days, who in the antenatal period or before going to work was analyzed by a specialist as having preeclampsia.

Control Group: Women confessed to post natal ward who conveyed dur-ing going before 2 days and did not had Preeclampsia amid pregnancy.

Pre-eclampsia (ICD-10 code 014) was characterized as a diastolic blood pres-beyond any doubt of in any event 90 mmHg on at least two sequential events 24 hours separated or a diastolic pulse of in any event 110 mmHg on any one oc-casion in addition to proteinuria (one 24-hour pee accumulation with an absolute protein discharge of at any rate 300 mg or two 1+ on a pee dipstick).. Every day all conveyed ladies satisfying the criteria for Preeclamp-sia case were selected into the examination. Same no of controls were then se-lected every day by irregular determination of outstanding beds. Case and control were selected inside 2 days of conveyance and educated assent was taken. Coordinating among cases and controls was not performed in light of the fact that huge numbers of the socio-statistic parameters are suspected hazard factors for PE. Data was gathered from emergency clinic case sheet of the ladies and by talking the Study subject herself. On the off chance that, a patient was torpid after

conveyance, the history was taken when she recaptured awareness or from relatives who went with her. Ladies, who conveyed before multi week of development independent of the result, were rejected from study. Pallor was characterized as Hemoglobin < 11g/dl. A ladies was considered non veggie lover on the off chance that she took any non vegan dish (barring egg), at any rate once every week over the most recent one month.

All the data was gathered utilizing a Predesigned, semi-organized investigation Performa to dispense with account predisposition. Potential hazard factors for study were chosen based on writing survey and organic plau-sibility for a relationship with both the presentation and result.

Measurable examination: Data got from study Performa was entered in MS Excel to figure Master Chart. Consistent factors were abridged as mean and standard deviation while absolute factors were summa-rized as extent (%). Unpaired t-test was utilized for examination of con-tinuous variable while Chi-square test was utilized for investigation of Categori-cal variable. Hazard was evaluated by count of Odds Ratio in Bivariate examination. Step savvy Multiple Logistic Regression investigation was done to discover indicators of Preeclampsia. All factors, found essentially associ-ated with Preeclampsia, were entered in Regression model. Likelihood of autonomous variable in holding Regression model was kept<0.05 while that of evacuation as >0.10. Every single factual estimation were finished by utilizing Med Calc.14.2.1.0 programming. P<0.05 was taken as noteworthy.

RESULTS:

Present investigation included 180 preeclampsia cases and 180 controls. The greater part of the investigation populace had a place with 21– 30 years old. More preeclampsia

ladies (25%) had a place with ≤20 years when contrasted with controls (17.8%). The two gatherings did not vary altogether in connection to instruction, religion, occupation and financial status. Bivariate investigation found that pre-eclampsia was altogether connected with provincial living arrangement (p=0.033), joint family type (p=0.025), low training of head of family(p=0.007), primiparity (p<0.001), youthful age at menarche (11-12years) (p<0.001), Anemia (P=0.034), Family history of preeclampsia (p<0.001) and hyper-pressure (p=0.007) and Non veg. diet (p=0.042). (Table 1-4). There was 1.22 occasions more hazard in joint family in bivariate

investigation. Additionally illiter-ate, center and graduate moms were having 1.05, 1.30 and 1.25 occasions more hazard. 1.33 occasions more hazard was discovered when the age at origination was between 21 to 25 years. Rh positive moms were having 2.7 occasions more hazard and moms having family ancestry of hypertension were observed to be at 2.8 occasions more danger of creating preeclampsia. In like manner non vegan moms have 1.63 occasions danger of preeclampsia.

Youthful age at menarche (11-12 years) was fundamentally more among pre-eclampsia (46%) when contrasted with controls (23%). Ladies with menarche at 11 &12 years had more than thrice the danger of preeclampsia as com-pared to those with menarche at 14 years. Preeclampsia was likewise signifi-cantly connected with primiparity. The danger of preeclampsia in primipara was more than twice (OR=2.39; 1.23-4.65) when contrasted with those with third equality. Preeclampsia was not observed to be essentially connected with history of past fetus removal, bury pregnancy period and sex of last offspring of multiparous ladies (Table-2). Paleness was observed to be asso-ciated with preeclampsia (P=0.034), anyway no affiliation was found among preeclampsia and ANC attributes, TT vaccination, IFA tablets, twin pregnancy or gestational diabetes (Table-3). Individual his-tory of preeclampsia and Family history of hypertension were likewise signifi-cantly connected with preeclampsia (table 4). Non veg. diet was observed to be essentially more among Preeclampsia cases (37.2%) when contrasted with controls (26.7%) (Table-4). Non veggie lover had chances of Preeclampsia 1.6 occasions than that in vegans. Smoking and tobacco biting was not observed to be related with preeclampsia.

The factors that were observed to be noteworthy in bivariate examination were then entered in the relapse model for stepwise different relapse investigation. Age >30 years, Preobese (BMI=25-29.9), large (BMI≥30 Kg/m²), Primiparity, period of menarche at 12 years and rustic home were observed to be free hazard factors related with Preeclampsia (ta-ble-5).

On applying different calculated relapse, patients with age >30 years were found to have 2.87 occasions danger of preeclampsia when contrasted with age <30 years. Primipara moms had 4.5 occasions chance when contrasted with mul-tipara moms. When contrasted with ordinary and underweight, preobese and fat were having 3.23

occasions and 8.28 occasions more danger of PE separately.

Danger of Preeclampsia was 2.59 occasions high in patients with time of men-arche < 12 years when contrasted with those in which age >12 years. Thus rustic inhabitants were having 1.67 occasions higher hazard for preeclampsia when contrasted with urban occupants.

DISCUSSION:

Present investigation planned to decide the socio-statistic and clinical elements that expansion danger of Preeclampsia. However, numerous socio-demo-realistic variables were observed to be related with Preeclampsia in bivari-ate examination, different strategic relapse investigation chose out the inde-swinging danger factors for Preeclampsia.

Table 1: Distribution of Study Population according to Socio-demographic characteristics

Socio-demographic characteristics	Case		Control		Total		Odds ratio (95% CL)	P value
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%		
Age Group (years)	≤20	45	25.0	19	10.6	64	17.8	1.547(0.977-2.45)
	21-25	85	47.2	102	56.7	187	51.9	-
	26-30	36	20.0	52	28.9	88	24.4	0.831(0.497-1.38)
	>30	14	7.8	7	3.9	21	5.8	2.400(0.92-6.217)
Religion	Hindu	137	76.1	138	76.7	275	76.4	0.970(0.59-1.577)
	Muslim	43	23.8	42	23.3	85	23.6	-
Residence	Urban	56	31.1	80	44.4	136	37.8	-
	Rural	113	62.8	91	50.6	204	56.7	1.774(1.143-2.75)
	Slum	11	6.1	9	5.0	20	5.6	1.746(0.679-4.49)
Family Type	Nuclear	18	10.0	36	20.0	54	15.0	0.53(0.219-1.289)
	Joint	146	81.1	127	70.6	273	75.8	1.221(0.59-2.517)
	3 generation	16	8.9	17	9.4	33	9.2	-
Education	Illiterate	70	38.9	65	36.1	135	37.5	1.533(0.837-2.81)
	Primary	26	14.4	24	13.3	50	13.9	1.542(0.73-3.257)
	Middle	21	11.7	15	8.3	36	10.0	1.992(0.868-4.57)
	High	26	14.4	37	20.5	63	17.5	-
Occupation	Post High school	14	7.78	22	12.2	36	10.0	0.906(0.39-2.091)
	Graduation /PG	23	12.8	17	9.44	40	11.1	1.925(0.86-4.297)
	House Wife	160	88.9	161	89.4	321	89.2	0.944(0.486-1.84)
	Working	20	11.1	19	10.6	39	10.8	-
Education Head of family	Illiterate	53	29.4	57	31.7	110	30.6	1.051(0.536-2.06)
	Primary	45	25.0	24	13.3	69	19.2	2.120(1.003-4.480)
	Middle	22	12.2	19	10.6	41	11.4	1.309(0.57-3.007)
	High	23	12.8	26	14.4	49	13.6	-
Socio-economic status	Post H Graduate	15	8.33	36	20.0	51	14.2	0.471(0.207-1.07)
	Honors'	20	11.1	18	10.	38	10.6	1.256(0.538-2.94)
	I	2	1.11	0	0.0	2	0.6	NA
	II	4	2.2	4	2.22	8	2.22	1.044(0.246- 4.43)
Socio-economic status	II	85	47.2	76	42.2	161	44.7	1.168(0.70-1.951)
	III	45	25	47	26.1	92	25.6	--
	IV	46	25.6	53	29.4	99	27.5	0.906(0.513-1.60)

Maternal age >30 years was found to expand the danger of Preeclampsia (OR=2.87; 1.03-7.99). Different studies.8-25-26-28 have likewise revealed advertisement vanced maternal age >30/35 years to be related with Preeclampsia. Expanded time of ladies is a significant hazard factor most likely due to in-wrinkled villous response prompting pre-eclampsia in a lady more noteworthy than 30years, as has been found in other studies.13-15 Age of menarche at 12 years was observed to be a huge

hazard factor for Preeclampsia (OR=2.59; 1.53-4.40), like finding of Ramesh et al 4 (2014). Early menarche (≤ 12 y) has been related with expanded danger of CVD occasions in different investigations conceivably interceded by expanded adiposity related with early menarche.25 Present examination observed Prim equality to be an inde-swinging danger factor for improvement of Preeclampsia (OR=4.51; 2.76-7.36) as has been found in numerous studies.24,25-27-32-33

Table 2: Distribution of Study population according to obstetric characteristics

Obstetric characteristics	No.	Case		Control		Total		Odds ratio (95% CL)	P value
		%	No	%	No.	%			
Age at Menarche (years)	11	10	5.6	4	2.2	14	3.9	4.53(1.222-16.800)	<0.001
	12	73	40.6	38	21.1	111	30.8	3.482(1.686- 7.192)	
	13	79	43.9	98	54.4	177	49.2	1.461(0.741-2.88)	
	14	16	8.9	39	21.7	55	15.3	-	
	15	2	1.1	1	0.6	3	0.8	3.625(0.305-3.153)	
Parity	1	117	65.0	56	31.1	173	48.1	2.388(1.226-4.651)	<0.001
	2	30	16.7	81	45.0	111	30.8	0.423(0.206-0.870)	
	3	21	11.7	24	13.3	45	12.5	-	
	4	8	4.4	14	7.8	22	6.1	0.653(0.229-1.86)	
Age at 1ST Conception	5	4	2.2	5	2.8	9	2.5	0.914(0.217- 3.856)	0.034
	≤ 20	103	57.2	118	65.6	221	61.4	--	
	21-25	72	40.0	62	34.4	134	37.2	1.330(0.865- 2.046)	
previous Abortion	>25	5	2.8	0	0.0	5	1.4	NA	0.501
	No	37	20.6	31	17.3	68	18.9	1.244(0.732-2.112)	
Inter pregnancy period	Yes	143	79.4	149	82.7	292	81.1	-	0.476
	<3 years	36	57.2	79	63.7	115	61.5	0.759(0.409-1.410)	
Sex of Last Child	≥ 3 years	27	42.9	45	36.3	72	38.5	-	0.885
	Male	28	44.4	55	44.5	83	28	1.004(0.545-1.848)	
	Female	35	55.6	69	55.6	104	35	-	

Table 3: Distribution of Study population according to present pregnancy characteristics

ANC characteristics	No.	Case		Control		Total		Odds ratio (95% CL)	P value
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%		
Completion of ANC	No	81	45	83	46.1	164	45.6	0.956(0.63-1.448)	0.916
	Yes	99	55	97	53.9	196	54.4	-	
Trimester of 1st ANC visit	1	74	41.1	74	41.1	148	41.1	-	0.948
	2	88	48.9	94	52.2	182	50.6	0.936 (0.607-1.45)	
	3	10	5.6	11	6.1	21	5.8	0.909 (0.364-2.27)	
	Incomplete	4	2.22	0	0.00	4	1.11	-	
TT immunization	Complete	176	97.8	180	100	356	98.9	-	0.131
	Not taken	23	12.8	17	9.44	40	11.1	1.207 (0.55-2.640)	
IFA tablets taken	<50	67	37.2	57	31.7	124	34.4	1.048 (0.58-1.886)	0.218
	50-100	53	29.4	73	40.6	126	35.0	0.648(0.36 -1.165)	
	100	37	20.6	33	18.3	70	19.4	-	
Gestational Diabetes (N=135)	No	18	20.7	7	14.6	25	18.5	1.528(0.588-3.97)	0.520
	Yes	69	79.3	41	85.4	110	81.5	-	
Gestation	Single	172	95.6	169	93.9	341	94.7	-	0.637
	Twin	8	4.4	11	6.1	19	5.3	0.715(0.280-1.82)	
	Normal	35	19.4	18	10	53	14.7	-	
Hemoglobin level	Mild Anaemia	19	10.6	30	16.7	49	13.6	0.326 (0.15- 0.73)	0.034
	Moderate Anaemia	107	59.4	118	65.6	225	62.5	0.466(0.249- 0.87)	
	Severe Anaemia	19	10.6	14	7.8	33	9.2	0.698(0.285-1.71)	

Table 4: Distribution of Study population according to Clinical characteristics

		Case		Control		Total	P value
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	
BMI	Under weight	17	9.4	20	11.1	37	10.3
	Normal	102	56.7	136	75.6	238	66.1
	Preobese	41	22.8	20	11.1	61	16.9
	Obese	20	11.1	4	2.2	24	6.7
Blood Group	A	22	15.8	28	21.1	50	18.4
	AB	20	14.4	23	17.3	43	15.8
	B	49	35.3	51	38.0	100	36.8
	O	48	34.5	31	23.3	79	29
Rh factor	Positive	131	94.2	114	85.7	245	90.1
	Negative	8	5.8	19	14.3	27	9.9
personal History of	Preeclampsia	18	28.6	0	0.0	18	9.6
	Hypertension	0	0	0	0.0	0	0
	Diabetes Mellitus	1	0.6	0	0.0	1	0.3
Family History	Renal Disease	0	0	0	0.0	0	0.032
	CVD	0	0	0	0.0	0	<0.001
	Preeclampsia	1	0.6	0	0.0	1	0.3
Diet	Hypertension	40	22.2	20	11.1	60	16.7
	Non Vegetarian	67	37.2	48	26.7	115	31.9
	Vegetarian	113	62.8	132	73.3	245	68.1
					NA		<0.001
1.	In Multiparous women				2.28	(1.27-4.09)	0.007
					1.631	(1.042-2.551)	0.042
					-		

Table 5: Multiple Logistic Regression analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Odds ratio	95% CI value	P
Age<30 years (Reference category)	-	-	-	-	
Age>30 years	1.05429	0.52293	2.869 9	1.0298-7.9984	0.
Normal and underweight (Reference category)	-	-	-	0.438	
Preobese (BMI 25-29.9 kg/m ²)	1.17387	0.33953	3.234 5	-	
Obese (BMI≥30 Kg/m ²)	2.11400	0.61334	8.281 3	-	
Multiparity (Reference category)	-	-	-	1.6626-6.2925	0.
Primiparity	1.50664	0.24977	4.511 6	0.005	
Age of menarche > 12 years (Reference category)	-	-	-	2.4889-27.5537	0.
Age of menarche < 12 years	0.95307	0.26933	2.5937	0.006	
Urban residence (Reference category)	-	-	-	-	
Rural residence	0.51211	0.25004	1.6688		1.52 99- 4.39
Constant	-1.6805				

This is on the grounds that demure equality is because of starting trophoblastic attack and how the mother responds to it. The disappointment of the ordinary attack of trophoblastic cells prompts maladaptation of the winding arterioles, which are identified with the causa-tion of pre-eclampsia.³⁴ In this examination, Rural Residence was found to a critical hazard factor for advancement of Preeclampsia. This related with the discoveries of a national cross sectional examination (NFHS-05-06) by Sutapa Agrawal et al.³⁵ In present investigation, BMI 25-29.9 Kg/m² (Preobese; OR=3.23; 1.66-6.29), and BMI $\geq$ 30Kg/m² (hefty; OR=8.28; 2.89-27.55) were observed to be free hazard factors for Preeclampsia. Overweight and corpulence have been accounted for as critical hazard factor by many studies

CONCLUSION:

Age>30 years, Preobese, Obese, Primiparity, early time of menarche (12 years) and Rural living arrangement as critical indicator for advancement of Preeclampsia. The greater part of these variables are non-modifiable, however can be utilized to screen ladies dursing antenatal visits to distinguish those at higher danger of Preeclampsia.

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